

EFFECTIVE USE OF DIGITAL TOOLS FOR ENGLISH TEACHING

Temirova Samiya Mukhitdinovna
Asia International University

Abstract: The article examines the linguodidactic potential of using some Internet resources in English classes. The work describes the techniques for using such digital tools as Yandex.Forms, Quizlet, Ahaslides, digital boards, QR codes; the advantages of their use over traditional forms of educational activity in foreign language classes at a university are outlined.

Keywords: digital tool; digital competencies; foreign language; university; student

The development of a modern digital educational environment, which today has great potential for improving the quality of education, has become very relevant. Currently, the educational process requires not only traditional approaches to teaching, but also unique methods of teaching students. The age of technology allows professors to come up with great ideas using digital tools, especially in teaching foreign languages. The use of an electronic board in the educational process is one of the most striking examples of how digital tools fuel students' enthusiasm in mastering complex topics, for example, when reading foreign literature that is not adapted for people for whom this book is not written in their native language. Broadcasting presentations, reports, curricula, students who are good at visual learning, according to the typology of the most effective learning methods, can achieve outstanding success in learning almost any aspect of the language. Psychologist Richard E. Meyer is the author of a study on the study of educational materials using multimedia, based on the model of information processing in the brain. He said: "Multimedia is about the principle that learning from words and pictures is more effective than learning from words alone." For the process of teaching foreign languages, such types of visualization as linguistic (verbal-speech) and non-linguistic (object-pictorial) are considered important. The central place is occupied by linguistic clarity, which exists in speech samples, grammatical rules and schemes, lexical units, in graphic and auditory texts, as well as video films. It is based on the norms of language use, on its authentic exemplary character and, as can be seen from the previous list, can be expressed in different forms - visual and auditory.

Virtual whiteboards such as Miro, Ziteboard, Witeboard, sBoard, BitPaper, etc. have been used by teachers around the world for over 10 years, both for distance learning and in-person classes. This tool allows for collaborative work between teachers and students, as well as

introducing a creative element into the learning process. Virtual whiteboards provide the opportunity for collaboration, posting different types of files and information, and the main advantage is that all course-related materials are structured and always available for study. Thus, a virtual whiteboard can become a platform for interaction between teachers and students throughout the semester. Information can be posted in different presentations: as a news feed, familiar to students thanks to social networks (one of the presentation options), as a map, timeline, graphically designated cause-and-effect relationships.

Prezi is a digital software for creating interactive presentations. According to research, Prezi's innovative way of helping you create presentations – by zooming in – results in more effective, persuasive, efficient and engaging presentations, which helps to better understand the information. In addition, it allows students to use the online translation mode. When the presentation is in a foreign language, students can click on the text and find the correct equivalent of the word in their native language. This technique can be used not only while reading the presentation. Recently, students and teachers have a tendency to watch movies, programs and videos for educational purposes right during the lessons! Using such digital tools in teaching helps to get acquainted with the natural language of their people. For example, watching movies in English allows people to learn English in real situations. You can learn new expressions for use in everyday life. Not only pronunciation is important, but also body language. This method is also great for understanding the context of the pronunciation of a particular word.

One of the most convenient and effective digital tools in this regard is the Quizlet service. Quizlet is a website that allows you to create flashcards for memorization, form test tasks from them, including those with a limited time for completion, and also conduct an interactive survey during a seminar. Memorization is based on visualization - figurative note-taking, during which abstract concepts receive visual, auditory or kinesthetic embodiments in memory. Students gain access to the module using a link that the teacher attaches to the virtual board in the corresponding "Vocabulary" section and can use it to repeat and consolidate lexical material. Moreover, students can create their own lexical modules and share them also through the virtual board or messengers.

A word cloud can be used as an effective tool for practicing new vocabulary. A word cloud is a visual representation of text information, which is most often used to graphically

highlight the most significant or frequently occurring words in a certain text. A word cloud can be generated automatically not only from the text, but also from specially specified words and expressions, for example, from a certain set of terms.

Yandex.Forms allow you to quickly and in a convenient format check your understanding of a read text or audio recording, as well as your knowledge of terms and grammar rules in the form of test tasks. As part of foreign language classes, these services are suitable for saving, analyzing, and subsequently working with lists of words and expressions for memorization and self-control (translation from English to Russian and vice versa for home reading) or any other data.

The use of a QR code as a link to an assignment during a seminar has generated positive reactions and interest among students. QR codes are useful for many teaching and learning tasks in higher education. QR code, or quick response code, provides the ability to quickly access digital information by pointing the camera of a mobile device at it, which, having captured the code, instantly offers a link to go to the desired site or page.

Ahaslides.com is a resource that allows you to create interactive presentations. With this tool, you can create a wide variety of tasks: from simply choosing the right answer to a question to conducting online quizzes, brainstorming and quizzes. Students have the opportunity to join the resource through a generated QR code and participate both individually and in small teams. It is worth noting that, despite the seemingly unnecessary gaming activity within the educational process, this format helps to diversify the work of students at the seminar, attract attention to serious and sometimes complex material due to, at first glance, an entertaining component.

The key characteristics of the modern world in the context of the digital economy are:

- a sharp increase in the volume of data;
- change in communication;
- freedom of development;
- increase in the number and speed of emergence of new technologies, changes in production.

Active introduction of various means of information and communication technologies

reorganizes the learning process, in particular, it is necessary to build a new methodology for teaching individual disciplines within the information and educational environment. As a result, the question of regulating the interaction of participants in the educational process arises. Organization of training within the framework of a system built on ICT means requires a certain set of rules governing the methods of communication, transmission of information, etc. The teacher is faced with the task of not only creating an information environment, but also ensuring the effective functioning of the system. In addition, technical equipment of educational institutions is one of the priority tasks, the solution of which is based on organizational and economic factors.

Thus, the use of the digital tools listed in this article will allow the student to master these competencies and be in demand in the labor market.

Literature:

1. Siraeva , M.N. On the relationship between the concepts of " humanization of education" and " humanitarianization of education" // Issues of teaching methods at the university. 2022. Vol . 11. No. 3. P. 8-21.
2. Akulenko , YG Psychological and Pedagogical Conditions for Forming Motivation for Learning Foreign Languages by Students of Non-Linguistic Universities in the Intercultural Aspect // Pedagogy and Psychology: Theory and Practice. 2022. No. 1 (25). P. 5–13.
3. Kuznetsova, M.N. Specifics of students' motivation to study English through the content component of educational material // Kazan Science. 2020. No. 5. P. 84–86.
4. Chermenina , E.N. Online boards. Using an interactive online board in foreign language lessons 2022. P. 128–133.